

taken from the top of 100 random tillers at the postflowering stage.

Leaves of tall varieties had wider leaf attachment angles than dwarf varieties (see figure). The difference is clear in the second and third leaves. But all leaves of Lalnakanda had closer angles than did dwarf varieties. Incorporation of acute leaf attachment angle in short-leaved dwarfs could result in better plant types where light interception would be less. Plant populations per unit area could be increased without adversely affecting photosynthetic rates. The trait is linked with a simply inherited rudimentary juncture condition and could be incorporated easily into the desired plant type. ■

Angles of leaf attachment of different rice varieties observed at Bhagalpur, India.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

A preliminary study on the specific gravity of rice grain

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Most Sri Lankans prefer red rices. But with the introduction of high yielding varieties, the number of red rice varieties in cultivation has decreased considerably. A preliminary study used specific gravity to compare rice color and grain weight.

Twenty rice varieties (10 red and 10 white), including both recommended varieties and elite lines, were grown under identical conditions during the 1980 dry season. Rice yield was dried in the shade to 14% moisture. Fifteen-gram samples from both brown rice and polished rice were drawn. Grain weight was determined by the specific gravity bottle method using kerosene oil.

Results suggest that the specific gravity of white rice is significantly higher than that of red rice (see table). Polishing increased the specific gravity, which could be attributed to removal of the high fat content of the bran.

Yield is the primary objective in varie-

tal improvement work in Sri Lanka. It is possible that the reduction in the number of red rice varieties grown is due to an unconscious selection against red grains, which have a lower weight than white. ■

Specific gravity measurements of rice in Sri Lanka.

Specific gravity ^a			
Red rice		White rice	
Brown	Polished	Brown	Polished
1.4000	1.4260	1.4120	1.4390

t-value ^b for color (red & white):

Brown rice = 2.942**

Polished rice = 3.106**

Milling (brown & polished):

Red rice = 5.733**

White rice = 5.978**

^a Mean of 10 samples. ^b **significant at .01 level.

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Breeding high-quality and high-yielding varieties of rice in Afghanistan

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Rice consumers in Afghanistan are quality conscious. Local varieties are high quality, with long, slender, translucent grains that cook into excellent plaw or biriani. Two very popular varieties, Barah and Lawangin, are grown extensively in the northern and the eastern areas. They are tall growing with weak straw and poor response to fertilization; hence productivity is low.

To increase yield potential, the two local varieties were crossed with a high yielding culture; IR790-28, at IRRRI. Bulk seed for growing the F₃ was received in 1973. Selection of desirable recombinants was carried out in F₃ to F₆ plants grown under high-level fertility (120-60-60 kg NPK/ha) at the Pos-i-Shan Agricultural Research Station at Baghlan.

Thirty high-yielding cultures from IR790-28/Barah and 37 cultures from IR790-28/Lawangin met the quality

standards of the local varieties. These cultures were tested in replicated varietal trials in 1975-1980 at the research stations at Baghlan in the northern zone and at Jalalabad in the eastern zone. Five cultures were selected for further testing in demonstration plots in farmers' fields. Their average yields in varietal trials is given in the table.

The new cultures gave 26.8% to 95.8% more yield than the local variety at Baghlan. At Jalalabad, the yield increase ranged from 11.8% to 221.1%. The cultures derived from IR790-28/Barah gave average higher yields than those from IR790-28/Lawangin.

The agroclimatic conditions at Baghlan seem conducive to high yield. Cultures 76-1-1 and 89-4-2 from IR790-281/Barah responded very well with yields of 10.2 and 12.5 t/ha. Besides high soil fertility at Baghlan, the main factor contributing to high yield was long sunny days. The average sunshine during the rice growing season was 9 to 11.6 hours daily. ■

Performance of new high-quality and high-yielding cultures in varietal trials at Baghlan and Jalalabad Research Stations, Afghanistan, 1975-80.^a

Culture, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Increase	
		t/ha	%
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Baghlan)</i>			
89-1	7.2	1.5	27.4
Local variety	5.6		
76-1-1	10.2	3.9	60.7
Local variety	6.4		
89-4-2	12.5	6.1	95.8
Local variety	6.4		
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Jalalabad)</i>			
89-1	6.1	4.2	221.1
Local variety	1.9		
76-1-1	5.7	3.5	157.8
Local variety	2.3		
89-4-2	4.3	2.1	90.4
Local variety	2.3		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Baghlan)</i>			
10-5	6.8	1.4	26.8
Local variety	5.3		
10-1-3-4	7.0	2.4	51.9
Local variety	4.6		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Jalalabad)</i>			
10-5	5.0	2.2	76.9
Local variety	2.8		
10-1-3-4	4.1	0.4	11.8
Local variety	3.7		

^aYield data were averaged.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Screening rice varieties for bacterial blight resistance

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Bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) disease became widespread in Bangladesh after the introduction of high yielding rice varieties. Six F₂ crosses and their parents — BR3, BR4, IRATOM24, IRATOM38, and Dular — and two high-yielding, early-maturing gamma-ray induced M₇ mutants and their parents — Mut 1-1, Mut 1-2, and IR8 — were screened for resistance in the field February-July 1980.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 25 × 20 cm spacing. The plants were artificially inoculated by the clipping method at flowering stage. None of the tested materials were completely free from infection. Only BR4-

Reaction of crosses, mutant strains, and varieties of rice inoculated with an isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* at flowering stage in Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Cross, mutant strain, or variety	Disease reaction ^a
BR3/IRATOM24	MS
BR3/IRATOM38	MS
BR3/Dular	MS
BR4/IRATOM24	MS
BR4/IRATOM38	MR
BR4/Dular	MS
BR3	MS
BR4	MR
IRATOM24	MS
IRATOM38	MS
Dular	MS
Mut 1-1	MR
Mut 1-2	MR
IR8	S

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

IRATOM38 and Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were moderately resistant. The parent IR8 of the mutants appeared susceptible (see table). ■

Reaction of some deepwater rice varieties to *Ditylenchus angustus*

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Tiem Dot San, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a serious disease of deep-

water rice in the Mekong Delta. In thousands of infested hectares, yield losses ranged from 20 to 100%. Almost all local deepwater rice varieties are susceptible.

The coleoptile inoculation method, with 10 adult nematodes per germinated seed, was used to test 34 deepwater var-

Reaction of 34 deepwater rice varieties to *D. angustus*, University of Cantho, Vietnam.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)	Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)
BKN6986-8	26	70	BKN6986-11-3	55	88
CNL53	30	55	CNL231 B-B	56	87
Jalaj	39	65	CNL180	56	98
Yodaya	42	75	IR5857-3-2E-2	57	84
BKN6986-113	42	79	Trang Tep	58	88
BKN6986-51	43	74	BKN6986-45	58	100
Sulpan	44	75	B1050 C-Mr-18-1	59	91
PG56	45	81	BKN6986-29	59	84
BKN6986-57	47	65	BKN6986-70	59	96
Cula	47	87	BKN6986-44	60	88
HTA7204	50	85	Chenabsel	61	92
Trung Hung	50	85	CNL319	62	92
81050 C-MI-26-3	51	85	IR5825-41-2-P4	63	89
BKN6986-66-2	52	86	CNL241	64	95
TR5825-41-2-P1	53	86	BKN6986-81-5	65	92
BKN6986-67	54	91	Nang Tay Dum	67	93
TR5857-64 IE1	55	87	IR5825-114-3P2	78	96